

D1.2. Project Quality Management Plan

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
PQMP	Project Management Quality Plan
CBE JU	Circular Bio-Based Europe Joint Undertaking
PO	Project Officer
WP	Work Package
MC	Management Committee
GenA	General Assembly
EAB	External Advisory Board
GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
EU	European Union
F&T	Funding and Tenders

Executive Summary

This Project Quality Management Plan (PQMP) is a deliverable report for the SuperBark project, funded by the Circular Bio-Based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU). The report defines the management structure and procedures implemented in the project to facilitate the coordination and communication between different management structures, support the decision-making processes, and ensure quality in the execution and reporting of project activities. This PQMP is primarily intended to be used by the SuperBark consortium members but can also serve as example of best practices in project quality management to beneficiaries of other collaborative research projects.

The management structure in the SuperBark project is composed of the Project Officer (PO) Coordinator, Work Package (WP) leaders, Management Committee (MC), General Assembly (GenA), and External Advisory Board (EAB), each with clearly assigned roles and responsibilities. The Coordinator is responsible for the overall coordination and management of the project, represents the consortium towards the CBE JU, and is the only one communicating with the PO. The WP leaders monitor the progress and risks in their own WPs and ensure high quality implementation of the tasks according to the project plan. The Coordinator and the WP leaders form the MC, which is the supervisory body for the execution of the project and is supported by consortium members with specific roles such as the Data Manager, Quality Manager, Gender Equality Officer, Ethics Mentor, and Exploitation Officer. The MC reports to the GenA as the ultimate decision-making body of the SuperBark consortium. The EAB provides advice and feedback on the project activities and assists the GenA in decision-making when necessary.

The management procedures included in this PQMP include guidelines for reporting deliverables and milestones as well as for monitoring and assessing risks. Deliverables, milestones, and risks are integral elements of project reporting and quality control and constitute contractual obligations defined in the Grant Agreement (GA). Another essential aspect to ensure progress and quality of project implementation is to establish efficient and regular communication among consortium members and management bodies. For this purpose, meetings having different targets, participants, periodicity, etc, are organized in the project and outlined in this PQMP. Finally, the managing of project related documentation is briefly presented.

Introduction

The deliverable D1.2. Project Quality Management Plan is created to establish a quality management system for the SuperBark consortium and promote high quality implementation and reporting throughout the project lifetime. As stated in the GA, the targets of the PQMP are to ensure i) management of project related documentation, ii) monitoring and quality control of project deliverables and milestones, and iii) risk contingency management. In this PQMP, management of project documentation is addressed only from the point of view of storing project documents and ensuring high quality reporting. Details on collection, processing, and management of all data and documents created in the project are described in a separate deliverable report, the Data Management Plan (D1.3 and updated versions D1.5 and D1.8).

This PQMP contains information about the SuperBark project, the management structure, and the quality management processes. The plan is based on the guidelines of the European Committee on quality management as well as on the Grant and Consortium Agreements (CA) of the project. The PQMP supports these agreements but does not replace or overrule them. The PQMP is primarily intended to be used by the SuperBark consortium members but can also serve as example of best practices in project quality management to beneficiaries of other collaborative research projects.

SuperBark project

The SuperBark project (<https://superbark.eu>) exploits natural components of softwood bark, a major side stream of the forest industries, to develop $\geq 95\%$ bio-based adhesives and coatings for wood panels and packaging paper that meet the performance, safety, and sustainability requirements of industry and consumers. The development of adhesives and coatings is guided by safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) assessments, including results from toxicology, recyclability, and biodegradability studies, and is further complemented with techno-economic evaluations and social and market analyses. The outcomes of the project are shared with relevant stakeholders to ensure communication, dissemination, and exploitation of the results.

The main objectives in SuperBark are to:

1. Produce bio-based components for adhesives and coatings from industrial softwood bark using VTT's novel alkaline extraction technology.
2. Develop and optimise $\geq 95\%$ bio-based adhesives for plywood, particleboard, and medium density fibreboard using extracted polyphenols from bark that have unprecedented properties beyond the state-of-the-art.
3. Develop and optimise $\geq 95\%$ bio-based coatings for plywood and packaging paper using bark-based cellulose nanofibers and polyphenols that have unprecedented properties beyond the state-of-the-art.
4. Develop an SSbD framework and related criteria supporting the development of sustainable adhesives and coatings using bark components.
5. Apply process design, system dynamics modelling, and data analyses as digital tools to support the design and market integration of the bark-based adhesives and coatings.
6. Communicate, disseminate, and exploit the outcomes of the project to relevant stakeholders in order to increase awareness of the new technologies, products, and associated opportunities.

The solutions developed in SuperBark are expected to diversify the bio-based product portfolio and increase their range of application, while improving the sustainability, circularity, and health and safety profile of the new bio-based products compared to current fossil-based benchmarks. Specific impacts of the project are:

1. Preventing the release of 18 million tons of CO₂ per year in the European Union (EU) through diversion of bark from current incineration practices to production of bio-based components for adhesives and coatings.
2. Improving human and environmental safety by restricting the use of ≥ 2 million tons of formaldehyde and other harmful chemicals in adhesives and coatings.
3. Increasing the recycling of at least half million tons of engineered wood and paper packaging products.
4. Creation of up to 4000 direct jobs by installation of bark processing facilities across the EU.

General project information

The SuperBark project, funded by the CBE JU under the call HORIZON-JU-CBE-2022: Bio-based coatings, barriers, binders, and adhesives, is a 4-year project with a total budget of nearly 4.5 million €. The project consortium consists of 12 partners: Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy (VTT; Coordinator), Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Forderung der Angewandten Forschung EV (FHG), Rigas Tehniska Universitate (RTU), Holzforschung Austria Osterreichische Gesellschaft fur Holzforschung (HFA), Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), Institut za Celulozo in Papir (ICP), Fundacion Tecnalia Research & Innovation (Tecnalia), CLIC Innovation Oy (CLIC), Adler-Werk Lackfabrik Johannberghoffer GmbH & Co KG (Adler), Metsaliitto Osuuskunta (Metsä), Goricane Tovarna Papiirja Medvode dd (Goricane), and Kastamonu Entegre Agac Sanayi ve Ticaret Anonim Sirketi (KEAS). General information on the SuperBark project is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. General project information

Action full title	Safe, sustainable and high performance adhesives and coatings from industrial softwood bark
Short name	SuperBark
Call & topic	HORIZON-JU-CBE-2022-R-02
Type of Action	Research and Innovation Action
Granting authority	Circular Bio-Based Europe Joint Undertaking
Grant Agreement No	101112447
Starting date	01.09.2023
Project duration	48 months
Coordinator	Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy (VTT)
Maximum grant	4 468 890.75 €

Project Management Structure

A clear management structure facilitates the overall coordination and management of the project as the responsibilities are clearly distributed and the decision-making protocol is pre-defined. The management structure of the SuperBark project is shown in Figure 1. The roles and responsibilities of the management bodies are found in the GA and CA of the project and are summarized below.

Figure 1. Management structure of the SuperBark project.

Coordinator

The project Coordinator carries out tasks assigned to it as described in the GA and CA. The Coordinator represents the consortium towards the CBE JU and is the only one communicating with the PO. The Coordinator is responsible for the overall coordination and management of the project, and in particular shall be responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the parties with their obligations according to the CA and GA.
- keeping the address list of members and other contact persons updated and available.
- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the granting authority (i.e., CBE JU).
- transmitting documents and information connected with the project to any other parties concerned.
- administering the financial contribution of the CBE JU and fulfilling the financial tasks described in Section 7.2.
- providing, upon request, the parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the parties to present claims.

WP leaders

The WP leaders are responsible for the activities carried out in their WPs with the help of the task leaders and the contributing partners. The WP structure and their interactions in the SuperBark project are shown in Figure 2. The WP leaders organise WP-level meetings to monitor progress, assess potential and critical risks, and ensure high quality implementation of the project plan. The status of the WPs is followed by monthly progress reports collected by the WP leaders and shared with the Coordinator.

Figure 2. Work packages and their interactions.

Management Committee

The WP leaders together with the Coordinator form the MC, which is the supervisory body for the execution of the project and shall report to and be accountable to the GenA. The MC (Executive Board in the CA) meets and collects information on the progress of the project, at least every 6 months but preferably every 3 months, examines that information to assess compliance with the project plan and, if necessary, proposes modifications of the plan to the GenA. The MC meetings take place online, latest one month before the Consortium meetings. The MC also supports the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the CBE JU.

The MC is assisted in their supervisory functions by several members with specific roles. The *Quality Manager* monitors the quality of the project outcomes and deliverables according to the guidelines of this PQMP. The *Data Manager* is responsible for managing the project data and for creating and updating the Data Management Plan. The *Gender Equality Officer* oversees that gender dimension is considered during project implementation, the *Ethics Mentor* monitors any ethical issues involved and how they are handled, and the *Exploitation Officer* supervises and guides the actions towards effective exploitation of the project results.

General Assembly

The GenA is the highest decision-making body of the consortium and consists of one representative from each party. The GenA shall make decisions on the project content, finances and intellectual property rights, evolution of the consortium (e.g., entry or withdrawal of partners, change of coordinator), breaches and litigations, and appointments (e.g., MC and EAB members). The GenA shall meet at least once per year, preferably in person during the organization of Consortium meetings.

Executive Advisory Board

The EAB is composed of one representative of each Advisory Board member. The EAB shall assist the consortium parties when implementing the project by providing information, advice, and feedback, and shall also support the GenA in decision-making when considered necessary. The EAB can also contribute to the communication of project results to external stakeholders. At least one online meeting between the EAB and the consortium is organised annually.

Project Quality Management

Quality of implementation in the SuperBark project is ensured by a clear division of roles and assignments, structured communication between consortium members and the different management bodies, and continuous reporting. A quality management process has been established in which, first, the WP leaders monitor the progress of the work carried out in their WPs, with the help of the task leaders and other contributing partners, and report to the Coordinator. Second, the MC (composed of the WP leaders and the Coordinator) is responsible for monitoring the overall progress and quality of the project and reports to the GenA. The MC is supported by the Data Manager, Quality Manager, Ethics Mentor, Gender Equality Officer, and Exploitation Manager in their quality assessment. Third, the GenA evaluates the progress and quality of the project implementation and decides on possible corrective measures to be applied. If necessary, the GenA shall be assisted by the EAB in their decision making. Finally, the Coordinator reports to the PO who supervises that the implementation and quality of the project is in compliance with the GA.

Continuous reporting is part of the quality management process and includes the reporting of deliverables, milestones, critical risks, and any other requested project indicators or documents. The reporting process and schedules for deliverables, milestones, and risks are described more closely in the next chapters; the processes and schedules have been approved by the GenA. Continuous project reporting also occurs in Consortium meetings where the progress of the WPs and the overall project are presented and discussed among consortium members. In addition to continuous reporting, periodic project reports composed of technical and financial parts are delivered to the CBE JU as defined in the Article 21 of the GA. The Coordinator is responsible for submitting all the reports and project related documents to the PO through the Funding & Tenders (F&T) Portal.

Deliverables and milestones

Deliverables and milestones are an integral part of project reporting and quality control, and constitute contractual obligations that must be completed according to the schedules defined in the GA. The WP leaders are responsible for ensuring that the work done in their WPs progresses as required to complete the deliverables and reach the milestones. However, the lead beneficiary for each deliverable is responsible for providing that specific deliverable.

The deliverables are reported using the SuperBark deliverable template, which is a Word document stored in the project's Teams workspace. The deliverable must be completed by the lead beneficiary and sent to the WP leader, who approves it before sending it to the Coordinator for review. The WP leader sends the deliverable to the Coordinator (who also acts as Quality Manager) at least 2 weeks before the submission deadline. The lead beneficiary must ensure that the deliverable sent for review is of high quality, follows good research practices, and agrees with the description and expectations from the GA. If the Coordinator considers that changes to the deliverable are needed, the deliverable report is then sent back to the beneficiary for editing. Any requested modifications to the deliverable need to be ready at least 4 days before the submission deadline. Once the deliverable is ready, the Coordinator submits the deliverable through the F&T Portal and notifies the PO. The submission of the deliverables is made by the Coordinator latest on the last day of the due month. A copy of the submitted deliverable is stored in pdf format in the SuperBark Teams workspace under the channel "Final deliverables". Any possible delays in the completion of the deliverables must be notified as soon as possible by the lead beneficiary to the WP leader and Coordinator, who will immediately notify the PO about the delay.

The project milestones are regularly discussed in the MC and Consortium meetings to ensure that they are reached in time. Reaching a milestone assigned to a specific WP is reported by the corresponding WP leader by writing a short description and sending it to the Coordinator (who also acts as Quality Manager) at least 2 weeks before the submission deadline. If the Coordinator considers that changes to the milestone description are needed, the report is then sent back to the WP leader for editing. Any requested modifications to the milestone description need to be ready at least 4 days before the submission deadline. Once the milestone description is ready, the Coordinator submits it through the F&T Portal and notifies the PO. Any possible delays in reaching the milestone must be notified as soon as possible by the WP leader to the Coordinator, who will immediately notify the PO about the delay. A contingency plan will then be drafted to assess the impacts of the delay and propose alternative actions if necessary.

Risk Management

Similar to deliverables and milestones, risk management is also an integral part of project reporting and quality control as stated in the GA. Continuous monitoring and reporting of the project progress enables the identification of emerging risks well in advance of deadlines. Risk management includes identifying and assessing the risks, creating plans for risk avoidance and/or mitigation, and implementing and following up the effects of the mitigation actions. Risk assessment is conducted according to the likelihood and impact of the identified risk (Figure 3).

Critical risks related to management, administration, or implementation of the work in the WPs were identified during the project proposal preparation and before the project initiation, and risk mitigation strategies were proposed. Any new risks identified must be communicated immediately to the WP leader who prepares a mitigation plan and presents it to the Coordinator. Critical risks

need to be communicated immediately, in addition to the WP leader, also to the Coordinator who will then assess the need for an extraordinary MC meeting.

Evaluation of risk class in projects	CONSEQUENCES			
		Minor (1)	Harmful (2)	Serious (3)
LIKELIHOOD	Unlikely (1)	1 Negligible No actions	2 Minor Follow-up	3 Moderate Actions advisable
	Possible (2)	2 Minor Follow-up	3 Moderate Actions advisable	4 Notable Necessary actions
	Likely (3)	3 Moderate Actions advisable	4 Notable Necessary actions	5 Unacceptable Immediate and obligatory actions

Figure 3. Assessment of risks based on their likelihood and impact.

The risks and their associated information such as assessment date, description of the risk, risk assessment category, mitigation plan, and responsible person for implementing and monitoring the mitigation actions are registered in an Excel file available to all partners in the SuperBark Teams workspace. This file is updated continuously based on discussions about risks in the MC and Consortium meetings, and immediately after new risks are identified or the assessment of previously identified risks changes.

Communication and meetings

Regular communication within the consortium is performed using email, phone, or the chat in the Teams workspace, and through online, hybrid, and face-to-face meetings. Different types of meetings are organized to discuss and agree on project implementation, monitor progress and quality, and present information or results to other project members or external stakeholders. The different types of meetings organized in SuperBark are listed in Table 2. Meetings of the MC and GenA are arranged by the Coordinator, while Consortium meetings are organised jointly by the Coordinator and the hosting partner. Both the Coordinator and the hosting partner prepare the meeting agenda together while the hosting partner is responsible for arranging all practicalities related to the meeting (booking venues, catering, etc). In addition to the regular meetings listed below, specific WP meetings and meetings between different project members are organized on need basis.

Table 2. Meetings organised in the SuperBark project.

Type	Objective	Participant	When
Kick-off meeting	Introduce project members and their roles, set clear practices for management, confirm shared understanding and initial plans.	All partners' representatives and key persons.	Once in M1.
GenA meetings	Make decisions related to the project's direction.	One representative of each consortium partner.	At least once a year.

Consortium meetings	Report progress of the work to all consortium members, enable face-to-face discussions.	Consortium meetings open to all consortium members.	Twice per year.
MC meetings	Ensure progress of the work, discuss execution of the work and risk management	WP leaders and the Coordinator	At least twice per year
Review meetings with CBE JU	Review the results of the reporting period.	CBE JU representative, external reviewers, consortium member representatives.	M21, M39 and M48.
EAB meetings	Present project results and impact to the EAB, collect feedback and advice of EAB members.	Advisory Board, Coordinator, WP leaders, other members requested by the WP leaders.	At least once a year.

Specific details on communication and dissemination practises are not included in this PQMP and will be available in a separate deliverable, Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (D6.1 and updated versions D6.3 and 6.5).

Project documentation

All project documentation, including but not limited to agreements (i.e., GA, CA), reports, agendas, presentations, minutes of meetings, contact lists, and templates for reporting, are stored and available in the SuperBark Teams workspace. The presentation and reporting of project results, as well as any other project related communication documents, are prepared using the templates specifically made for the SuperBark project to have a common format, identity, and quality. The Coordinator is responsible for the administration of the project's Teams workspace, granting access rights to the project members, and ensuring that it is safe to use. Details on collection, processing, and management of all data and documents created in the SuperBark project are not described in this section because they are part of a separate deliverable report, the Data Management Plan.